

Spectrophotometric Determination of the Dissociation Constants of some Drugs in Methanol+Water Mixtures

S. C. DUTTA and S. C. LAHIRI*

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani-741 235

Manuscript received 10 April 1990, revised 22 August 1991, accepted 31 December 1991

The dissociation constants of some drugs available as hydrochlorides have been determined spectrophotometrically in various compositions of methanol+water mixed solvent. The variation of the dissociation constant has been explained in terms of the free energy changes involved in the transfer of drugs from aqueous to aquo-alcoholic mixed solvents, of their molecular and ionic forms.

MOST of the organic compounds of medicinal interest are weak bases, relatively insoluble in water (the dominant biological fluid) though weak acids are not uncommon. The weak bases are usually converted to their hydrochlorides and effectively used as such and administered orally. The compounds are present as cations and some of these compounds form stable ion-pairs in solution. However, in most cases transport across the tissue boundaries occurs largely in their neutral non-ionic forms. It is apparent that absorption of drugs depends not only on the lipid solubility of non-ionic form but also on the dissociation constant of the acid or base and pH of the media on either side of the membrane¹.

It is, therefore, desirable to study the dissociation constants of these drugs in water. Since it is difficult to study the dissociation equilibria in lipids, it may be useful to determine the dissociation constants of these drugs in different mixed solvents. With these objects in view, we have attempted to determine the dissociation constants of the following drugs: promethazine hydrochloride, chlorpromazine hydrochloride, trifluopromazine hydrochloride, isoxsuprine hydrochloride and papaverine hydrochloride.

The phenothiazines are slightly soluble in basic forms. They are known to form micelles in aqueous solution and the CMC values are in the order 10^{-2} – 10^{-3} M². Moreover, the CMC, molecular aggregation and aggregation numbers are dependent on pH and concentration of electrolytes². These conditions preclude the determination of the dissociation constants of these compounds by potentiometric method using H₂-electrode or pH-metric method using glass-calomel electrodes.

The spectrophotometric method is best suited in the present case where a small concentration (10^{-5} M) of drug is sufficient for accurate measurements of the dissociation constants of these drugs. We, therefore, determined the dissociation constants of the drugs spectrophotometrically in aqueous and methanol+water mixtures.

Experimental

Promethazine hydrochloride was recrystallised from ethylene dichloride. Chlorpromazine hydrochloride was dissolved in water and filtered. Sufficient amount of ether was added to the solution which precipitated the salt. The precipitate was then dried. Trifluopromazine hydrochloride was recrystallised from xylene, papaverine hydrochloride from ethanol+water mixtures and isoxsuprine hydrochloride from water. Methanol (spectroscopic grade, S.D.'s) was used as such. The traces of water, if any, in the organic solvent were neglected. All the reagents were of AnalaR grade.

HClO₄, NaOH, HCl and succinic acid were estimated in the usual way. The pH of the solutions in the aqueous as well as in the mixed solvents was maintained using Na₂BO₄ – HCl buffers in most cases and KH₂PO₄ – Na₂HPO₄ buffers in the case of papaverine hydrochloride (above 44 wt% of methanol the measurement was avoided due to precipitation of phosphate).

The peaks in the absorption curves in acidic and alkaline solution of the drugs (in aqueous and mixed solvents) are as follows: promethazine hydrochloride 299 and 251 (acidic), 302 and 254 nm (alkaline); chlorpromazine hydrochloride 307 and 255 (acidic), 310 and 253 nm (alkaline, in mixed solvent), trifluopromazine hydrochloride 305 and 254 (acidic), 278 and 257 nm (alkaline, in mixed solvent), isoxsuprine hydrochloride 274, 269 and 219 (acidic), 292, 278 and 241 nm (alkaline); papaverine hydrochloride 310, 284 and 250 (acidic), 325, 314 and 279 nm (alkaline). The pK values were determined spectrophotometrically as described before^{2,3}. The wavelengths of measurement are: promethazine 305; chlorpromazine 307; trifluopromazine 307; isoxsuprine 296; papaverine 312 nm.

Spectrophotometric measurements were made using a Hitachi double beam spectrophotometer. The measurements were carried out at 298 K.

The weight percentage of the organic solvents were obtained by mixing the calculated amounts of two solvents. The dielectric constants of the mixed solvents were calculated from the data given in the literature⁵.

The pH of the solutions were determined using an Orion EA 920 ion analyzer with an accuracy of 0.001 pH unit. However, we have rounded the pH-values upto two decimal places. Appropriate corrections for measuring the pH in mixed solvents had been made as suggested by Van Uitert⁶ and others⁷⁻⁹.

Results and Discussion

The dissociation equilibria for the isoelectric reaction can be written as

where B is chlorpromazine, papaverine, promethazine *etc.*

$$\text{where } K_a = \frac{C_B \times C_{H^+}}{C_{BH^+}} \times \frac{f_{H^+}}{f_{BH^+}} = \frac{C_B \times C_{H^+}}{C_{BH^+}} \quad (2)$$

assuming $f_{H^+} = f_{BH^+}$. However, due to variations of the ion-size parameters of H⁺ ion and drug cations, slight variations in f_{H^+} and f_{BH^+} are expected but cannot be taken into account. We usually try to avoid the use of 'inert electrolytes'¹⁰ in the measurement of pK values to avoid 'salt effect' as far as practicable so that the 'medium effects' can be determined. But we are forced to use 'buffer solutions' to measure the pK values of these drugs in the pH regions 4-9. The mean pK-values of some of the tranquillisers and antihistaminic drugs are recorded in Table 1. The results have been found to be accurate within 0.02 pK units.

All the drugs are cationic and the reactions are 'isoelectric' (i.e. BH⁺ ⇌ B + H⁺ type) in nature. Therefore, the change in solvent should have little effect on the dissociation constants of these 'isoelectric reactions'. However, the pK-values decrease with increase in methanol content of the medium similar to those observed in case of other cationic acids^{4,11,13}. However, no sharp minimum is noted

in the solvent composition range. The decrease can be ascribed to solute-solvent interactions. The dissociation should increase due to increased solubility of the neutral forms of these drugs in more lipophilic mixed solvents and increased basicity of the solvent mixtures.

The pK values of isoelectric reactions when plotted against mole fraction of organic solvent and 1/ε show deviations at about 0.2-0.25 mole fraction of methanol (34%) above which variations against 1/ε are highly pronounced. This indicates that the solute-solvent interactions are more important than electrostatic part. The pK-values for chlorpromazine and trifluorpromazine in water (obtained from extrapolation) come out to be 8.88 and 8.49 respectively.

In order to comprehend the nature of the ion-solvent interactions we have tried to analyse the results in terms of single ion values.

It is seen from equation (1),

$$\Delta G_i^0(1) = \Delta G_i^0(H^+) + \Delta G_i^0(B) - \Delta G_i^0(BH^+).$$

The ΔG_i⁰(1) (negative) is composed of ΔG_i⁰(H⁺) (-ve), ΔG_i⁰(B) (-ve) (solubility of B increases with methanol content) and ΔG_i⁰(BH⁺) which appears to be increasingly positive. But in view of the difficulty in determining ΔG_i⁰(B), we are not in a position to say much regarding the ion-solvent interactions of the cations. We have the values for G_i⁰(B) - G_i⁰(BH⁺) = ΔG_i⁰(1) - ΔG_i⁰(H⁺) given in Table 2.

The ΔG_i⁰(H⁺) values in methanol + water mixtures have been taken from our earlier work¹². There is definitely some uncertainty in the ΔG_i⁰(H⁺) values as they have been determined using extrathermodynamic assumption with its inherent limitations. But all the methods suffer from limitations due to extrathermodynamic assumptions. In spite of the limitations, ΔG_i⁰(H⁺) values in methanol + water mixtures determined by us are in good agreement with the ΔG_i⁰(H⁺) values reported by Wells¹⁴, Kalidas *et al.*¹⁵ (except at 20 wt%), Tomkins¹⁶ and Alfenaar *et al.*¹⁷ qualitatively and to some extent quantitatively at low percentages of methanol if we consider the wide variations in results reported in

TABLE 1—DISSOCIATION CONSTANT OF DRUGS (AS HYDROCHLORIDE) IN METHANOL+WATER MIXTURES AT 298 K

Methanol wt %	1/ε × 10 ³	pK _a				Papaverine
		Promethazine	Chlorpromazine	Trifluorpromazine	Isoxsuprine	
0.0	1.27	8.91	(8.88) ^a	(8.49) ^a	8.49	6.69
8.1	1.33	8.80	8.78	8.41	8.41	6.61
16.0	1.40	8.67	8.69	8.33	8.29	6.52
25.2	1.48	8.52	8.58	8.22	8.19	6.39
34.4	1.57	8.34	8.47	8.09	8.08	6.26
44.7	1.69	8.25	8.37	8.01	7.99	6.11
54.2	1.84	8.11	8.22	7.92	7.92	—
64.1	2.01	7.98	8.14	7.80	7.82	—
75.9	2.25	7.91	8.07	7.71	7.74	—

^aObtained from extrapolation.

TABLE 2—FREE ENERGY OF TRANSFER (kJ mol^{-1}) OF DRUG FROM WATER TO METHANOL+WATER MIXTURES AT 298 K

MeOH wt%	$\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}^+)$	$\Delta G_i^{\circ}(1)$					$\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{B}) - \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{BH}^+) = \Delta G_i^{\circ}(1) - \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}^+)$				
		Promethazine	Chloropromazine	Trifluopromazine	Isoxsuprine	Papaverine	Promethazine	Chloropromazine	Trifluopromazine	Isoxsuprine	Papaverine
8.1	-0.6	-0.63	-0.57	-0.45	-0.46	-0.46	-0.03	0.03	0.15	0.14	0.14
16.0	-1.3	-1.37	-1.09	-0.91	-1.14	-0.97	-0.07	0.21	0.39	-0.16	0.33
25.2	-1.8	-2.23	-1.71	-1.54	-1.71	-1.71	-0.43	0.09	0.26	-0.09	0.09
34.4	-2.1	-3.26	-2.34	-2.28	-2.34	-2.45	-1.16	-0.24	-0.27	-0.24	-0.35
44.7	-3.2	-3.77	-2.91	-2.74	-2.85	-3.31	-0.57	0.09	0.46	0.35	-0.11
54.2	-4.0	-4.57	-3.77	-3.25	-3.25	—	-0.57	0.23	0.75	0.75	—
64.1	-5.0	-5.31	-4.22	-3.93	-3.82	—	-0.31	0.78	1.07	1.18	—
75.9	-5.5	-5.71	-4.62	-4.45	-4.26	—	-0.21	0.88	1.05	1.24	—

In water, $[\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{B}) - \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{BH}^+)]$ values in kJ mol^{-1} are : promethazine, 1138.24 ; chloropromazine, 1138.07 (obtained from extrapolation) ; papaverine, 1125.57 ; trifluopromazine, 1135.84 (obtained from extrapolation) ; isoxsuprine, 1135.84.

the literature. However, $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}^+)$ values in methanol+water mixtures determined recently by Abraham *et al.*¹⁸ based on the assumption $(\text{Ph}_4\text{P}^+, \text{Ph}_4\text{As}^+) = \text{Ph}_4\text{B}^-$ show both qualitative and quantitative disagreement with those reported previously. The $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}^+)$ values in ethanol+water mixtures determined in our laboratory¹⁸ are in good agreement quantitatively with the values reported by Popovych and Dill¹⁹ based on the TABBP₄ assumption. Thus, we consider the $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}^+)$ values used by us to be quite reliable. Moreover, $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}^+)$ values in all these solvent mixtures over the whole composition range are not available by other methods.

It is known that $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{B}) - \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{BH}^+)$ should be equal to $\pm \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{el})(\text{BH}^+)$. Since, $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{el})(\text{BH}^+)$ should be increasingly positive as we go from water to methanol, the results conclusively show that ion-solvent interactions is of importance in determining $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(1)$. In spite of limitations, it is apparent that the behaviour of these drugs are different from each other. $[\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{B}) - \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{BH}^+)]$ is negative and passes through a minimum at about 34 wt% of methanol for promethazine, for papaverine, the value is positive but passes through a minimum at 34 wt% (complete picture is lacking), and for isoxsuprine the minimum is observed at 34 wt%. However, fluctuations in these values are observed. The trend in chloropromazine is little different and we have to use extrapolated value of chloropromazine in water ($\text{pK}=8.88$) but marked change is observed near about 34 wt% of methanol.

It is difficult to infer structural changes from the free energy of transfer as structural changes are complicated functions of enthalpy and entropy changes. It is well-known that the addition of methanol first strengthens the three-dimensional water structure. Structure formation appears to be maximum at 0.2–0.3 mole fraction of methanol after which structural collapse begins²⁰. These are well reflected in $[\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{B}) - \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{BH}^+)]$ values vs composition curves (Fig. 1). The excess thermodynamic properties of mixing of MeOH+water mixture²¹ show a maximum in exothermic enthalpy of mixing at about $X_2=0.2$, a minimum in $T\Delta S$ at $X_2=0.3$ and

Fig. 1

a maximum in the positive free energy of mixing at about $X_2=0.5$ (X_2 = mole fraction of methanol).

It is expected that the structural changes associated with the dissociation of the cationic drugs in the solvent mixtures are reflected in $[\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{B}) - \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{BH}^+)]$.

All these compounds are characterised by the presence of hydrophilic and hydrophobic centres leading to two different types of hydration. Thus, both hydrophilic and hydrophobic interactions compete for water structure organisation^{22,23}. The addition of drug molecules to water causes the rupture of tetrahedral structures of water. When two non-polar regions come closer together, these regions are shielded to a greater extent from interaction with water molecules leading to the collapse of the quasicrystalline structure of water. The nature of hydrophobic interactions of drug molecules with water changes with the addition of methanol.

Since the nature of the interacting groups are different, the changes in thermodynamic properties are expected. The changes can be attributed to specific solvation effects and hydrophobic effects which act in the opposite direction. Specific solvation effects are dependent mainly on the composition of the solvent mixture being greatest for strongly solvated drugs. The hydrophobic effect, on the other hand, increases with the size of solute molecules and is maximum where maximum enhancement of the water structure occurs, i.e. in the region of 0.2–0.3 mole fraction of methanol. The increase in the size of the solute shifts the point of maximum structure-formation towards media richer in water^{22,23}.

It is apparent that with the increase in the hydrophobic character of the solvents, the dissociation of drugs increases and the neutral molecules will more readily go into the organic layer.

It is to be noted that the binding force between drugs and tissue proteins are primarily electrostatic in nature. Since drugs are present predominantly as cations at the physiological pH (7.4) and the proteins at pH 7.4 usually carry a negative charge (the isoelectric points of proteins are usually less than 7.4), strong plasma-protein binding is quite natural in such cases and this plasma protein binding is very much dependent on hydrophobic character of the side-chains (as well as on solvents). Plasma-protein binding can markedly affect the amount of free drug available for the rest of the system¹. The basic drugs with pK 6.0 and above are almost completely ionised in gastric contents and hence are not readily absorbed from the stomach^{24,25}.

The absorption process of the drugs is essentially a two-step process :

Thus, the pK values of the drugs, pH of the solution of the receptor site and the lipophilic character of the lipid membranes are important for drug absorption and physiological action.

References

1. J. B. STENLAKE, "Foundations of Molecular Pharmacology", The Althone Press of the University of London, 1979, Vol. 2, Chap. 3.
2. D. ATTWOOD and A. T. FLORENCE, "Surfactant Systems", Chapman and Hall, London, 1983, Chap. 4.
3. S. C. LAHIRI and S. ADITYA, *Z. Phys. Chem. (N.F.)*, 1964, **41**, 173, 469; 1964, **43**, 282; 1967, **55**, 6; *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, **30**, 2487.
4. D. K. HAZRA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1975, **79**, 335.
5. A. K. COVINGTON and T. DICKINSON in "Physical Chemistry of Organic Solvent Systems", eds. A. K. COVINGTON and T. DICKINSON, Plenum, 1973, p. 18.
6. L. G. VAN UITERT and C. C. HASS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 451.
7. U. C. BHATTACHARYYA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Z. Phys. Chem. (N. F.)*, 1966, **50**, 131.
8. R. G. BATES, "Determination of pH, Theory and Practice", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1973, pp. 276–277.
9. S. C. LAHIRI and S. ADITYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **51**, 319.
10. A. BHATTACHARYYA and S. C. LAHIRI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 971.
11. Ref. 8, Chap. 8 and reference therein.
12. D. SENGUPTA, A. PAL and S. C. LAHIRI, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1983, 2885.
13. A. K. BHATTACHARYYA, D. SENGUPTA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Z. Phys. Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1984, **265**, 372.
14. C. F. WELLS, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1973, **63**, 974.
15. C. KALIDAS, P. SIVAPRASAD and U. V. VENKATRAM, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1977, **32**, 791.
16. R. P. T. TOMKINS, Thesis, University of London, 1966.
17. M. ALFENAAR and C. U. DE LIGNY, *Recl. Trav. Chim. Pays-Bas*, 1967, **86**, 929.
18. M. H. ABRAHAM, T. HILL, H. G. LONG, R. A. SCHULZ and R. A. C. WATT, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1984, 489.
19. O. POPOVYCH and A. J. DILL, *Anal. Chem.*, 1969, **41**, 456.
20. G. BISWAS, S. ADITYA, A. BHATTACHARYYA and S. C. LAHIRI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 1137.
21. F. FRANKS and D. J. B. IVES, *Quart. Rev., London*, 1966, **20**, 1.
22. Y. POINTUD and J. JUILLARD, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1977, 1907.
23. N. DOLLET and J. JUILLARD, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1976, **5**, 77.
24. A. T. FLORENCE and D. ATTWOOD, "Physicochemical Principles of Pharmacy", 2nd. ed., McMillan, New York, 1988, Chaps. 9 and 10.
25. A. ADRIEN, "Selective Toxicity", 6th. ed., Chapman and Hall, London, 1979, Chaps. 3 and 10.